

Gross Anatomical Studies on the Vertebral Column of Indian Mongoose (*Herpestes javanicus*)

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ABSTRACT

Indian mongoose (*Herpestes javanicus*) is a small predatory mammal capable of surviving in a variety of habits including deserts, forests, agricultural and urban areas. Vertebral formula of the Indian mongoose is $C_7, T_{13}, L_7, S_3, Cy_{21-25}$. The transverse processes of 3rd to 5th cervical vertebrae were bifid and showed anterior and posterior processes whereas trifid in 6th vertebra. At the root of the transverse processes of 2nd to 6th cervical vertebrae showed foramen transversarium. In thoracic vertebrae capitular facets of adjacent vertebrae together form capitular cavities for heads of the ribs. Dorsal spinous processes were upward and backward in direction upto 10th thoracic vertebra, whereas the spine of 11th vertebra was vertical, and considered as "anticlinal vertebra". The transverse processes were small and less developed. The anterior articular processes of lumbar vertebrae were well developed and strongly curved medially. Posterior articular processes were projected laterally and their articular areas were facing laterally. Mamillary processes were present in first four lumbar vertebrae and the accessory processes were present in first 6 lumbar vertebrae except the 7th lumbar vertebra. The sacrum was formed by the fusion of three vertebrae. On the dorsal surface on either side of the articular processes two intervertebral foramina were present. The pelvic surface was deeply concave and showed two ventral sacral foramina. The first seven coccygeal vertebrae were typical vertebrae but beyond the seventh they were atypical vertebrae. The ventral surface of the bodies of 7th to 10th caudal vertebrae showed 'V' or 'Y' shaped haemal arches.

Key Words: Vertebral column, Indian mongoose and Gross Anatomy.

INTRODUCTION

Indian mongoose (*Herpestes javanicus*) is a small predatory mammal capable of surviving in a variety of habits including deserts, forests, agricultural and urban areas. The mongoose has five toes with retractable claws and a robust tapered tail. Many wild populations including mongoose has been pushed towards extinction (Roy, 2006) and no information is available on the anatomical features of skeletal system of the Indian mongoose. The axial skeleton plays important role in improving the gait efficiency with minimal energy requirement by their attachments with the limbs (Venkatesan *et al.*, 2015). Hence, the present study was undertaken to elucidate the anatomical features of the vertebral column of Indian mongoose.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in six Indian Mongooses. The six dead mongoose were collected and kept in normal water for maceration for 30 days at College of Veterinary Science, Proddatur,

Andhra Pradesh. After complete maceration the bones were cleaned thoroughly and recorded the gross anatomical features of bones of the vertebral column of mongoose.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vertebral formula of the Indian mongoose was: $C_7, T_{13}, L_7, S_3, Cy_{21-25}$

Cervical Vertebrae:

The cervical vertebrae were 7 in number.

Atlas:

It was atypical vertebra. It was in the form of small ring (Fig.1). The dorsal arch of the atlas was wide, convex and centre of the dorsal surface was rough for muscular attachment. The lateral masses showed two saddle shaped anterior articular areas for occipital condyles. Dorsal surface of the wings were concave and ventrally flattened. Two foramina pierced the wings, cranially alar foramen opened ventrally and connects the intervertebral foramen by a groove. Similar observations were also reported by Olude *et al.* (2013) in rats, whereas the alar foramen was transformed into

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alar notch in dogs and tiger as reported by Getty (2012) and Taluja *et al.* (2002a) respectively. The transverse foramen pierced the wing on its caudal aspect.

Axis:

It was an atypical vertebra. The dens was located at the middle of the cranial extremity of the body, which was pointed and long, and reached almost the occipital bone (Fig.3) like in dog (Getty, 2012) and in tiger (Taluja *et al.*, 2002b). The transverse processes were small and directed caudally and foramen transversarium was present at the base of the processes. The dorsal spinous process was very large and a strong plate-like structure. It was wide and thick anteriorly and became thin and narrow posteriorly (Fig.3). The spinous process was posteriorly terminated as tubercle in dog (Getty, 2012), tiger (Taluja *et al.*, 2002b) and it was grooved in rats (Olude *et al.*, 2013). The anterior notches were deeper than the posterior ones.

3rd to 5th Cervical Vertebrae:

These were typical vertebrae. Similar observations were also reported by Getty (2012) in dog and in Tiger (Taluja *et al.*, 2002c). The length of the transverse processes diminished from 3rd to 5th cervical vertebra (Fig.4). They were bifid and showed anterior and posterior processes. At the root of the transverse processes of each vertebra showed a foramen transversarium. It is in accordance with the observations made by Getty (2012) in dog, Taluja *et al.* (2002c) in tiger and Olude *et al.* (2013) in rats.. The length of spinous processes increased from 3rd to 5th cervical vertebra (Fig.4). Similar observations were also noted by Getty (2012), (Taluja *et al.*, 2002c) and Olude *et al.*, (2013) in dog, tiger and rat respectively.

6th Cervical Vertebra:

The length of the body was less compared to 5th cervical vertebra. The transverse process was trifid and it was divided into dorsal, anterior and posterior processes. At the root of the transverse processes, foramen transversarium was present. The length of the spinous process was more than that of the 5th cervical vertebra (Fig.4&5). The ventral spinous process was less prominent. Similar observations were also reported by Getty (2012) in dog, in tiger (Taluja *et al.*, 2002c) and in rat by (Olude *et al.*, 2013).

7th Cervical Vertebra:

The length of the body was less compared to 6th cervical vertebra. The transverse process was undivided. The length of the spinous process was more than that of the 6th cervical vertebra (Fig.4&6). Ventral spinous process was less prominent. There was no capitular facet on the body for first rib as the 1st rib articulates with the 1st thoracic vertebra only, whereas in dog the 7th cervical vertebra carried capitular facets for first rib (Getty, 2012), in Tiger

(Taluja *et al.*, 2002c) and in rat (Olude *et al.*, 2013).

Thoracic Vertebra:

Thoracic vertebrae were 13 in number. The length of the bodies was gradually increased from 1st to 13th thoracic vertebra (Fig.7). Capitular cavity for 1st rib was formed by 1st thoracic vertebra individually without the involvement of last cervical vertebra and also the last three thoracic vertebrae showed capitular facets individually for corresponding ribs as observed in dogs by Getty (2012). From 1st thoracic vertebra to the 10th thoracic the anterior articular areas were located at the base of the spinous processes. Whereas the anterior articular processes of 11th, 12th and 13th thoracic vertebrae were well developed and strongly curved and articular areas were medially placed. The posterior articular processes of 10th, 11th, 12th and 13th thoracic vertebrae were well developed and strongly curved and articular areas were laterally located 11th spine was vertical, so it was considered as "anti-clinal vertebra". (Fig.7). Similar observations were reported by Getty (2012) in dog. Transverse processes were absent in last three thoracic vertebrae. Mamillary processes were observed from 6th thoracic vertebra onwards, and they were distinct in caudal series i.e. from 10th to the 13th thoracic vertebra (Fig.7). Evans and Christensen (1964) in dogs reported that mamillary processes began from 2nd or 3rd thoracic vertebra and continued up to the last thoracic vertebra. Pandit (1994) in tiger reported that mamillary processes were seen only in 2nd to 10th thoracic vertebrae and in 12-13 thoracic vertebrae. In rats mamillary processes were observed from 10th to 13th thoracic vertebrae (Olude *et al.*, 2013). Accessory processes were observed from 7th thoracic vertebra onwards and they were prominent from 10th to the 13th thoracic vertebra. Similar observations were also reported by Evans and Christensen (1964), Getty (2012) in dog. Kumar (2008) in leopards reported that accessory processes were absent upto 10th and were well defined in 11th, 12th and 13th thoracic vertebrae. Nutrient foramina were noted in all thoracic vertebrae on their ventral aspect of the bodies.

Lumbar Vertebra:

Lumbar vertebrae were 7 in number. The length and breadth of the bodies increased from 1st to 7th lumbar vertebrae (Fig.8). Similar observations were reported by Evans and Christensen (1964) in dogs, Olude *et al.*, (2013) in rats. The spinous process of the last lumbar vertebra was vertical. Similar observations were also reported by Getty (2012) in dogs and Pandit (1994) in tiger. Mamillary processes were present in first four lumbar vertebrae (Fig. 8), contrary to that mamillary processes were observed in all lumbar vertebrae of dog by Evans and Christensen (1964) and Getty (2012), in tiger by Pandit (1994) and in rats (Olude *et al.*, 2013). The accessory processes were present from 1st to 6th lumbar vertebrae

except in the 7th lumbar vertebra (Fig. 8). Whereas Evans and Christensen (1964) and Getty (2012) reported in dogs, the accessory processes were well developed in first 3 or 4 lumbar vertebrae only. Pandit (1994) in tiger reported that accessory processes were observed up to 5th lumbar vertebrae, whereas they were absent in 6th and 7th lumbar vertebrae.

Sacrum:

The sacrum was formed by the fusion of three vertebrae. (Fig.10). Similar reports were noted by Evans and Christensen (1964), Getty (2012) in dog and Pandit (1994) in tiger, whereas Olude *et al.* (2013) reported that the sacrum of the rat was made up of 4 sacral vertebrae. Pandit (1994) in tiger and Olude *et al.*, (2013) in rat reported that spinous processes were not fused. On the dorsal surface on either side of the articular processes two intervertebral foramina were present. The wings were wide and consisted of articular area for the ilium (Fig.10). Transverse processes of the 2nd and 3rd sacral vertebrae were fused and plate like and directed downward and backward. Promonotary was distinct.

Coccygeal Vertebrae:

Coccygeal vertebrae varied from 21 to 25. Pandit (1964) observed 21 in tiger and Olude *et al.* (2013) reported 31-36 in rats. The first 7 vertebrae were typical vertebrae, thereafter they were atypical vertebrae. Only bodies were present in 11th to the last caudal vertebrae (Fig.12). Ventral surface of the bodies of 7th to 10th caudal vertebrae showed 'V' or 'Y' shaped hemal arches or chevron bones. Similar structures were observed in dog at 3rd 4th and 5th caudal vertebrae level (Getty, 2012), in tiger at 4th, 5th and 6th caudal vertebrae level (Pandey, 2014) and in rats at the level of 6th and 7th caudal vertebrae (Olude *et al.*, 2013). Spinous processes were present only in 1st and 2nd coccygeal vertebrae, Transverse processes were well developed in the first and bifid at their free ends in 3rd to 5th caudal vertebrae (Fig.11). Beyond 6th it was ridge like and disappeared from 11th caudal vertebra onwards (Fig.12). Articular processes were appeared upto the 7th caudal vertebra and from 8th onwards they were disappeared. The neural arches failed to meet from 8th caudal vertebrae onwards. Pandit (1994) in tiger and Olude *et al.* (2013) in rats reported that first 7 were typical vertebrae in tail.

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Figure. 1. The Photograph showing the dorsal surface of the atlas of Indian mongoose

Figure. 2. The Photograph showing the ventral surface of the atlas of Indian mongoose

Figure. 3. The Photograph showing the axis of Indian mongoose

Figure. 4. The Photograph showing the cervical vertebrae of Indian mongoose

Figure. 5. The Photograph showing the 6th cervical vertebra of Indian mongoose

Figure. 6. The Photograph showing the 7th cervical vertebra of Indian mongoose

Figure. 7. The Photograph showing the thoracic vertebrae of Indian mongoose

Figure. 8. The Photograph showing the lateral view of the lumbar vertebrae of Indian Mongoose

Figure. 9. The Photograph showing the dorsal view of the lumbar vertebrae of Indian Mongoose

Figure. 10. The Photograph showing the sacrum of Indian mongoose

Figure. 11. The Photograph showing the coccygeal vertebrae (1 to 8) of Indian mongoose

Figure. 12. The Photograph showing the coccygeal vertebrae of Indian mongoose